

THE ROLE OF SHADOWING METHOD IN IMPROVING OF STUDENTS' SPEAKING SKILLS

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Annotation: Today, many scientists in modern linguistics have developed a number of new methods for the development of students' speaking skills and applied them to the educational process. The following article talks about the importance of the “Shadowing” technique, which is considered one of such interactive methods, in the development of the speaking skills of students' who are learning English. The author gives examples of the advantages and disadvantages of the “Shadowing” technique.

Key words: “Shadowing” technique, oral speech, pronunciation, pronunciation competence, stress, stressed word, unstressed word, phonetics, phonology, speaking skill, speaking technique, interpreting skill.

Аннотация: Сегодня многие ученые-современники-лингвисты разработали ряд новых методов развития речевых навыков учащихся и применили их в учебном процессе. В следующей статье говорится о важности техники «Shadowing», которая считается одним из таких интерактивных методов, в развитии разговорных навыков студентов, изучающих английский язык. Автор приводит примеры преимуществ и недостатков техники «Shadowing».

Ключевые слова: метод «Shadowing», устная речь, произношение, произношенная компетентность, ударение, ударное слово, безударное слово, фонетика, фонология, речевое мастерство, техника говорения, умение устного перевода.

Annotatsiya: Bugungi kunda zamonaviy tilshunoslikda ko'plab olimlar talabalarning nutqini rivojlantirish uchun bir qancha yangi metodlar ishlab chiqishgan va ularni ta'lim jarayoniga tadbiiq etishgan. Quyidagi maqolada shu kabi interaktiv metodlardan biri hisoblangan “Shadowing” metodining ingliz tili o'rganuvchi talabalar nutqini rivojlantirishdagi ahamiyati haqida so'z boradi.

Muallif “Shadowing” metodining afzalliklari va kamchiliklari haqida misollar keltiradi.

Kalit soʻzlar: “Shadowing” metodi, ogʻzaki nutq, talaffuz, talaffuz meʼyorlari, urgʻu, urgʻuli soʻz, urgʻusiz soʻz, fonetika, fonologiya, nutq qobiliyati, nutq texnikasi, tushuntirish qobiliyati.

Speaking and pronunciation both relate to the same basic activity as both try to convey meaning to the listener. Having good pronunciation can help in normal communication, particularly regarding intelligibility (Jenkins, 2002). However, communication may fail if the listener misinterprets the message or the speaker mispronounces the words due to unfamiliar sounds or phonology. In order to communicate intelligibly, speakers need to use the appropriate stress. Brown (1992) stated that native speakers can notice stress in a variety of ways, such as when using contractions or indirectly via the absence of stress on words. However, foreign learners cannot be expected to automatically know the stress and therefore it is necessary for foreign learners to learn the stress pattern and phonological features.

Some experts share their thought about definition of shadowing technique. Yajima states: “shadowing was originally developed as a training technique for simultaneous interpreting in Europe and has gained much interest among language educators in improving the listening and speaking competence of learners as “shadowing” requires competence in both listening and speaking”.

It means shadowing is one of training technique which is gained language educators’ interests to improve listening and speaking competence.

Then, according to Nakanishi and Ueda, “shadowing was initially developed as a way for training simultaneous interpreters. “Shadowing is important and developed to simultaneous interpreters training”. Then, Shiota also states that “shadowing is one of the training techniques that used to improve interpreting skills and studies report that shadowing has recently become popular as a teaching method”. From the argument of Shiota, to improve interpreting skill, English teachers in many countries often use shadowing technique nowadays.

According to Katamba (1992), stress is primarily a matter of greater auditory prominence and it is essentially a perceptual phenomenon. Stressed syllables tend to have a higher pitch and longer duration than their non-stressed counterparts. They may also be louder than unstressed syllables. From a phonological angle, there is word stress and sentence stress. Speakers use stress to convey meaning to the

listeners and to emphasize certain information. Therefore, English language students need to learn the stress pattern in order to have better speaking and listening skills.

There are many activities that can be used to enhance speaking and listening skills, including 4-3-2, information gaps, and shadowing. This study focuses on shadowing, which was used as a potential way to enhance the students' knowledge of stress patterns as part of teaching pronunciation. There are many studies which focus on the shadowing activity for listening and speaking. Unlike repetition, which allows silent pauses for cognitive activities, shadowing does not give time for meaning but rather enhances phonology (Hamada, 2015). Kadota (2007) claims that shadowing enhances the students' speech perception, increases their working memory capacity, and strengthens the rehearsal process. Some studies carried out in an EFL context in Japan showed that shadowing is effective for improving listening comprehension skills. Murphey (2001) carried out conversational shadowing which involved “complete shadowing”, “selective shadowing” and “interactive shadowing”. They argue that shadowing may be a “fence rider” strategy, balanced between deliberate and automatized language use as shadowers are able to sound relatively fluent, beyond their individual competences, and stretch their abilities. Moreover, shadowing allows the listener to hear everything twice, providing more natural weight to the utterance from hearing and producing it.

Kadota (2012) introduces two types of shadowing: “pre-shadowing” (shadowing before learning the lesson content) and “post-shadowing” (shadowing after learning the lesson content). In pre-shadowing, learners can deliberately focus on the incoming sounds because those sounds comprise the only information on which they can rely. In post-shadowing, being familiar with the target passage can ease learners' anxiety (Hamada, 2011), which consequently lowers the psychological costs of shadowing. Against this background, the author was interested to explore whether shadowing is an effective technique to use in teaching receptive skills, through studying learners' improvement in producing the correct stress by using this technique.

Furthermore, according to Tamai, “shadowing is an active and highly cognitive activity in which learners track the heard speech and pronounce it as clearly as possible at the same time that they hear it”. From this explanation, shadowing makes the students track the speech and repeat it as same as possible at the same time they listen it.

According to Yo Hamada, Shadowing helps following fast speech which is one of the problems faced by non-native listeners. Native speakers tend to speak fast and use linking verbs to connect the speech which makes the non-native listener difficult to follow what they say. Learners try, follow, and pursue with quick speeches; this can help them to get used to listening to quick speeches. In theory, students eventually become accustomed to this speed, which consequently helps them listening better than before.

Shadowing has been categorized into some types. According to Murphey in Adachi (1997) there are varieties of shadowing. For example “lecture shadowing” is when listeners shadow a speaker silently in their mind when hearing a lecture. In “reading shadowing”, one person reads a passage when his/her partner shadows. “conversational shadowing” is conversation where listeners shadow each other out loud. “Complete/listening shadowing” indicates shadowing every word a speaker utters. Finally, “interactive shadowing” includes selected information and adds questions or comments, like a natural conversation. Except for lecture shadowing, shadowing can be either silent or aloud. The biggest advantage in shadowing is students’ involvement in the activity. According to the unknown writer (2010), there are many ways to shadow. They are:

- 1) “Full shadowing”. Say everything listeners hear. Use this in English class, not in “the real world”.
- 2) “Slash shadowing”. This is like full shadow but with pauses. This gives listeners more time to shadow. Use this in class. It is easier than full shadowing.
- 3) “Key word/last word” shadowing Say the most important words. Say the last words. Use this often! It shows the listeners are listening.
- 4) “About you” shadowing. Say what listeners hear. Change “I” to “you.” This is usually for English class. The listeners have to think about the sentence to do this.

In terms of the classification of shadowing above given by unknown writer, the researcher took a conclusion that the types of shadowing dealing with the speed are full shadowing and slash shadowing. Full shadowing is the listener listens and repeats directly what the speaker says without pause but slash shadowing is the listener listens and repeats directly what the speaker says with pause. However, based on using script, shadowing can be classified as direct shadowing and indirect shadowing. Direct shadowing is the listener listens and repeats directly what the

speaker says without looking at the script and indirect shadowing is the listener listens and repeats what the speaker says by looking at the script.

Shadowing technique is one of learning technique that is considered easy to be applied. The steps of Shadowing Technique are:

1. Listening to MP3/MP4 related to the topic.
2. Understanding vocabularies, intonation, and pronunciation from the audio or video.
3. Trying to imitate what the speaker says.
4. Repeating the steps until we can follow the speaker correctly in almost the same time.

Shadowing initially involves repeating the words of the speaker without modification. This allows the interpreter's brain, ears and mouth, working as they do in concert, to begin to reproduce the sounds and rhythms of the target language, without conscious mental effort, and begins to create the “linguistic muscle memory” naturally acquired by children learning their own tongue. This will require many tens of hours of actual speech production – it is essential that the language actually be voiced, or the exercise is useless.

According to some scientists also there are advantages and disadvantages of Shadowing Technique. As a technique in English, shadowing has some advantages. Someya demonstrates that “shadowing can help learners’ acquire prosodic features of a language, which creates a basis to improve listening skills”. It means shadowing is useful in learning process, especially in listening. It is not impossible to enhance this technique to increase students’ speaking performance, because listening and speaking are related.

As a technique, shadowing also has disadvantages. According to Ingrid, “shadowing exercises are purely mechanical exercises which, by teaching students to parrot words, are apt to reinforce their natural tendency to stick too closely to the speaker’s words”. In other words, shadowing technique is claimed as “too simple” technique because it makes the students only imitating the speaker. They cannot speak as their way.

The conceptual framework from this research:

The conceptual framework above explains the process to find out students' improvement in pronunciation. Students' face obstacles in the speaking process as they wrong in pronoun words correctly. The researcher used the shadowing technique in order to help students' speak well especially in order to make good pronunciation, by using Shadowing is a technique where students' listen to audio and then they repeat afterward in this research, the researcher use pre-test, treatment then post-test. Students' were encouraged to follow the speaker on the video as soon as possible by only having a short time to delay it. Actually shadowing is a cognitive and active activity where students' try to guess the words they hear and clearly say the words while listening continuously. So when students' say the words that they listen indirectly they get the new vocabulary and how to pronounce it correctly. By giving the shadowing technique students know how to pronounce the text well.

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